

TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES IN USING ONLINE EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES (OER) IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SAMPLE ONLINE EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS

Rosilyn B. Musca and Susan B. Pineda, Ph.D.

*Graduate School, Marinduque State College, Boac, Marinduque
Extension of Graduate Programs to Eastern Quezon College, Inc. Gumaca, Quezon,
Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study develops the perception of the teachers in relation to the benefits of using online resources in their educational activities, the impact of the Online Educational Resources (OER) in Schools Division of Quezon in the teaching and learning process. This was longitudinal research and it included teachers of various subjects. The key research instrument tends to address the teachers' insight for the benefits of using online resources. Taking into research that the nature of this study is of the evaluative character of teachers has been implemented by using questionnaires. The results show that teachers have a positive attitude towards usage of the online platform in their teaching, which also influences for their lessons to become more efficient and attractive for the learners and also for the teachers. As far as the usage of online resources for the learners' learning concerns, the findings of this research study indicate a positive attitude of the respondents in Schools Division of Quezon for the affirmative impact that the usage of online educational resources has for the learners' learning. This research study also indicated that there are still technical problems present which in many cases hindered present which the utilization of the online resources.

Keywords: *Teaching, Learning, Platforms, Online Resources*

INTRODUCTION

As a teacher working in an elementary or a secondary school, you likely need to face a crucial reality - having limited time to deal with all kinds of school duties, including developing lesson plans, creating teaching materials, and documenting student learning progress, etc. This reality in K-12 educational settings could be particularly overwhelming if you are a beginning teacher. Luckily, with the advent of technology and the emergence of K-12 Open Educational Resources (OER) more free and quality resources become available for K-12 teachers. OER allow teachers to save the time creating teaching materials from scratch, yet still have access to materials that support student learning engagement. OER have created an extra ordinary opportunity for educators to customize teaching and learning as well as sharing knowledge in various forms across communities, states, and even countries.

The DepEd Open Educational Resources (OER) is an innovative pathway to connect the disconnected schools with its prime role to support the requirements of the K-12 Curriculum. It focuses on the ICT Assisted Teaching and ICT Assisted Learning whereas the customization of localized materials is made possible to deliver quality, accessible, relevant and liberating education for all even for schools without strong internet facilities. The OERs are designed in such a way to cater the needs for interactivity, digitization and delivery of 21st Century Skills to make learners future ready. This is the beginning of revolutionizing education in the Philippines to teach minds, touch hearts and transform lives of learners. Welcome to the new era of learning. This is Digital Rise.

Embracing the use of OER will solve the challenges encountered by the public school system, especially the so-called Last Mile Schools or those schools in the far-flung areas in terms of access to learning materials and skills to create or reuse contents.

This scenario is true in the public elementary schools in Macalelon District, Division of Quezon. As a teacher-researcher, this issue is interesting to study to be able to determine the experiences of teachers in transitioning from textbooks to online instructional materials so as to apply in everyday teaching.

Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, data was gathered in order to address each of the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment; and
 - 1.4 Length of Service?

2. What are the teachers' experiences in using open educational resources in terms of following when grouped into demographic profile:
 - 2.1. Existence of online platforms;
 - 2.2 Online platforms as Instructional Materials;
 - 2.3 Advantages of Open Educational Resources; and
 - 2.4 Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources?
 3. Is there a significant difference on the teachers' experiences using open educational resources when grouped into profile?
 4. What are the problems encountered by teachers in using Online Instructional Materials?
 5. What are the coping strategies of teachers in addressing the challenges?
 6. What sample of open educational resources instructional material could be developed by the researcher?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher chose will use a survey research design because it is best served to answer the questions and the purposes of the study. The survey research is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. In other words, only a part of the population is studied, and findings from this are expected to be generalized to the entire population (Nworgu 1991:68).

Research Locale

The map into next page illustrated the Division of Quezon which considered as one of the four very large schools divisions in the Philippines. The Division of Quezon is headed by Dr. Merthel M. Evardome, CESO VI. She started her journey as Assistant Schools Division Superintendent in 2013, she assumed SDS post in the Division of Antipolo in January 2014, transferred to the Division of Laguna in July 2015. After six months January 6, 2016, she was appointed back to Schools Division of Quezon as Schools Division Superintendent. During her term, the Schools Division Office of Quezon continues to flourish and excel in many areas of governance. DepEd Quezon was hailed as the second-Best Performing Division in Region IV-A in 2017 and the first Best Performing Division in Region IV-A in 2018. The Division's Brigada Eskwela was also awarded twice as Hall of Fame Award in the National Brigada Eskwela. Lots of awards and recognitions were received by the division in sports, journalism, research and others. Facilities and physical improvements are noticeable and most importantly quality of service of all personnel are gearing towards excellence.

Figure 5 Map of the Division of Quezon

Quezon is a province of the Philippines in the CALABARZON Region located in the south of Luzon Island. Its capital is Lucena. Quezon province was named after former President Manuel L. Quezon who was born in Baler, a town which was then part of Tayabas. Quezon is famous for coconut-based cuisines, lambanog, longganisang Lucban, and pansit habhab.

The Quezon province is divided into 39 Municipalities, 1 Independent City, and 1 Component City: Agdangan, Alabat, Atimonan, Buenavista, Burdeos, Calauag, Candelaria, Catanauan, Dolores, General Luna, General Nakar, Guinayangan, Gumaca, Infanta, Jomalig, Lopez, Lucban, Lucena, Macalelon, Mauban, Mulanay, Padre Burgos, Pagbilao, Panukulan, Patnanungan, Perez, Pitogo, Plaridel, Polillo, Quezon, Real, Sampaloc, San Andres, San Antonio, San Francisco, San Narciso, Sariaya, Tagkawayan, Tayabas, Tiaong, Unisan.

DepEd Quezon encompassing of 953 schools; 771 Elementary and 182 Secondary Schools. 166 out of 182 are offering Senior High School Program. These schools are distributed in four congressional districts of Quezon. Quezon Province is composed of 1,543 barangays. The 953 schools are headed by a Schools' Division Superintendent and three Assistant Schools Division Superintendent serving with him in the field are 57 Public Schools District Supervisors, 271 Elementary School Principals, 107 Secondary School Principals, 45 Head Teachers and 310 Teacher-In-Charge.

The Division of Quezon, a winner on Innovations in Leadership, Governance and Management - Institutional Leadership and Direction Setting during the 6th Excellence in Educational Transformation Awards given by Bayan Academy in cooperation with ABS-CBN Foundation, Rex Bookstore, Knowledge Channel and DepEd, Garden Ballroom, Edsa Shangri-La Hotel, Mandaluyong last November 19, 2019.

Research Population and Sample

The respondents of this study were divided into Four (4) Congressional Districts in the Division of Quezon. Simple Random Sampling will be used where every element has an equal chance of getting selected to be part of the sample. The researcher first identified the population. Before a sample is chosen randomly, it is necessary to have a complete list of the population from which to select. After a list of population members has been constructed, the researcher prepared for a draw lots.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents for the study. In the 1st Congressional District, 8 teachers will be from the large schools, 4 teachers from the medium schools and 1 from a small school. Meanwhile, from the 2nd Congressional District, there are 7 teachers from large schools, 4 from medium schools and 1 from a small school. From the 3rd Congressional District, there are 5 teachers from large schools, 2 from medium schools and 1 from a small school. From the 4th Congressional District, there are 9 teachers coming from large schools, 8 from medium schools and 2 teachers from small schools.

Table 1*Distribution of Population*

Congressional District	School size	Teachers	
		Number	%
First	Large	8	15.38
	Medium	4	7.69
	Small	1	1.92
Second	Large	7	13.46
	Medium	4	7.69
	Small	1	1.92
Third	Large	5	9.62
	Medium	2	3.85
	Small	1	1.92
Fourth	Large	9	17.31
	Medium	8	15.38
	Small	2	3.85
Total		52	100

Research Instrument

A questionnaire designed by the researcher were used in the study. The questionnaire has eight sections: A, B, C, D, E, F, G, and H. Section "A" is about the respondents' profile, section "B", level of experiences; section "C", is there a significant difference on the teachers' experiences using open educational resources; section "D" is on the online platforms used, section "E" contains questions on the advantages with 12 indicators, Section "F" is on the disadvantages of using OER with 8 indicators; Section "G" is on the problems encountered. It has 6 indicators; section "H", on the other hand is on the coping strategies to be used to address the problems on using OER, which has 5 indicators. The instrument was structured in the modified Likert fashion, on a 5 – point scale, ranging from "highly experienced" (HE), "experienced" (E), to "moderately experienced" (ME) to "least experienced" (LE), and "not experienced" (NE). Subjects were then instructed to respond to their degree of agreement with the statements contained in the instrument.

Point Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 5.00	– Highly Experienced (HE)	The level of experiences is 81% to 100% in using OER.
4	3.40 4.19	– Experienced (E)	The level of experiences is 61% to 80% in using OER.
3	2.60 3.39	– Moderately Experienced (ME)	The level of experiences is 41% to 60% in using OER.
2	1.80 2.59	– Least Experienced (LE)	The level of experiences is 21% to 40% in using OER.
1	1.00 1.79	– Not Experienced (NE)	The level of experiences is less than 20% in using OER

The instruments were validated the following teachers in Macalelon Central Elementary School, Macalelon District. There are (2) two Master Teachers, Mrs. Elaine A. Delos Santos, Master Teacher II -English Coordinator, and Mrs. Maria Concepcion L. Edaugal, Master Teacher I-Mathematics Coordinator, and (1) one Macalelon District ICT Coordinator Mr. Rey E. Mallari. The certification of validation of research instrument were issued on 10th day of February 2023 at Macalelon Central Elementary School, Macalelon District.

Data Gathering Procedure

Questionnaires are the most common way of gathering data from a sample of individuals. Questionnaire is a list of questions each with a range of answers. It is also a format that enables standardized, relatively structured, data to be gathered about each of a large number of cases. Questionnaires are now commonly used at all levels of social research, from small scale students and community projects through to large-scale international surveys. The main common things between those surveys are the formulation of a set of questions sometimes and answers which are going to help the researcher to answer his research question or test his hypothesis

For this study, self-made questionnaire would be designed in the way that all types of questions except multiple choice questions will be used. For instance, open-ended questions will be given to receive the respondents' opinion about the level of experiences and online platforms used. Likert Scale will be used to answer the advantages, disadvantages, problems encountered and coping strategies in using OER questions for the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to the research ethics of anonymity, consent, and beneficence. the research ensured that the data gathered were secured and observed with the utmost consideration of data privacy. no personal information provided by the respondents was divulged in the study. in addition, the teachers who provided the data of learners were given a copy of the consent form to ensure they were aware of their participation. The

researcher explained in full detail the process of data gathering and assured that the data shall be treated with the utmost confidentiality. The teachers were also given the option to withdraw their participation if they felt there was a need for them to do so. Finally, the researcher informed the respondents that no benefits shall be provided to the respondents but the data they will be providing shall be helpful for the realizations and completion of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Various statistical tools such as frequency count, weighted mean, percentage, and rank is used to determine the profile of the respondents.

To determine the significance of agreement, the statistical analysis of the data in assessing the advantages and disadvantages of using OER in the Division of Quezon, Kendall Coefficient of Concordance W is employed (Siegel, 1988).

Where:

$$W = \frac{S}{\frac{1}{2} k^2 (N^3 - N)}$$

S = the numeration of square
 $\frac{1}{2}$ = is constant
R = refers to the number of groups
N = the number of items

The corresponding χ^2 formula will be used to determine the significance of agreement (Siegel, 1988).

$$\chi^2 = K (N-1) W$$

Significance level is set at 0.05.

Scope and Delimitation

The study is confined to the teachers' experiences in using online educational resources in the schools Division of Quezon: basis for the development of sample online educational resources instructional materials; online platforms being used, advantages and disadvantages, problems encountered, and coping strategies would be discussed in this study.

The study was conducted in the Schools Division of Quezon Province during the School Year 2023-2024. Respondents of the study are teachers. In addition, the profile of teachers was also gathered in terms of age, sex, educational attainment and length of service.

The respondents of the study are delimited to public elementary teachers in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Quezon.

RESULTS

Part I. The Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment and Length of Service.

Table 1

The Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment and Length of Service

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
26-35 years old	30	33.3
36-45 years old	24	26.7
46-55 years old	26	28.9
56-65 years old	10	11.1
Total	90	100.0
Sex		
Male	10	11.1
Female	80	88.9
Total	90	100.0
Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	10	11.1
College Graduate with masters' units	80	88.9
Total	90	100.0
Length of Service		
1-5 years	12	13.3
6-10 years	21	23.3
11-15 years	12	13.3
16-20 years	22	24.4
21-25 years	10	11.1
26-30 years	13	14.4
Total	90	100.0

Part II. The Teachers' Experiences in Terms of Existence of Online Platforms; Online Platforms Used as Instructional Materials; Advantages of Open Educational Resources; and Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources

Table 2.1.1

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Age

Indicators	Mean				SD	Total	
	26-35 years old	36-45 years old	46-55 years old	56-65 years old		Mean	VI
1. The Open Educational Resources offers convenience and flexibility for teachers.	4.33	4.21	4.35	4.10	.671	4.28	HE
2. Open Educational Resources meet high quality student-Tutor Interactions.	4.17	4.00	4.27	3.80	.678	4.11	E
3. Retention Rates are higher in Open Educational Resources.	3.97	4.00	4.23	3.90	.669	4.04	E
4. Open Educational Resources can supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources.	4.10	3.96	4.38	4.00	.690	4.13	E
5. Open Educational Resources must be free- both to give, to take and sharing.	4.10	4.00	4.31	4.20	.815	4.14	E
6. Open Educational Resources can reduce the cost of education for your students.	4.13	3.83	4.19	4.10	.716	4.07	E
7. Open Educational Resources can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities in the form of open images, open courseware, and self-assessment tools.	4.27	4.04	4.35	4.20	.700	4.22	E
8. Learners can benefit from OER's enhanced quality and flexibility of resources.	4.30	4.08	4.35	4.20	.659	4.24	HE
9. Open Educational Resources help learners in applying knowledge in a wider context than their course may otherwise allow.	4.13	4.08	4.15	4.10	.668	4.12	E

10. Open Educational Resources help support for learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer and social-informal learning approaches.	4.27	4.04	4.23	4.20	.685	4.19	E
Grand Mean	4.18	4.02	4.28	4.08	.695	4.15	E

Table 2.1.2

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Sex

Indicators	Mean			Total	
	Male	Female	SD	Mean	VI
1. The Open Educational Resources offers convenience and flexibility for teachers.	4.40	4.26	.671	4.28	HE
2. Open Educational Resources meet high quality student-Tutor Interactions.	4.00	4.13	.678	4.11	E
3. Retention Rates are higher in Open Educational Resources.	3.90	4.06	.669	4.04	E
4. Open Educational Resources can supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources.	3.80	4.18	.690	4.13	E
5. Open Educational Resources must be free-both to give, to take and sharing.	3.90	4.18	.815	4.14	E
6. Open Educational Resources can reduce the cost of education for your students.	3.90	4.09	.716	4.07	E
7. Open Educational Resources can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities in the form of open images, open courseware, and self-assessment tools.	4.10	4.24	.700	4.22	HE
8. Learners can benefit from OER's enhanced quality and flexibility of resources.	4.00	4.28	.659	4.24	HE
9. Open Educational Resources help learners in applying knowledge in a wider context than their course may otherwise allow.	3.80	4.16	.668	4.12	E
10. Open Educational Resources help support for learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer and social-informal learning approaches.	3.90	4.23	.685	4.19	E
Grand Mean	3.97	4.18	.695	4.15	E

Table 2.1.2

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Sex

Indicators	Mean		SD	Total	
	Male	Female		Mean	VI
1. The Open Educational Resources offers convenience and flexibility for teachers.	4.40	4.26	.671	4.28	HE
2. Open Educational Resources meet high quality student-Tutor Interactions.	4.00	4.13	.678	4.11	E
3. Retention Rates are higher in Open Educational Resources.	3.90	4.06	.669	4.04	E
4. Open Educational Resources can supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources.	3.80	4.18	.690	4.13	E
5. Open Educational Resources must be free-both to give, to take and sharing.	3.90	4.18	.815	4.14	E
6. Open Educational Resources can reduce the cost of education for your students.	3.90	4.09	.716	4.07	E
7. Open Educational Resources can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities in the form of open images, open courseware, and self-assessment tools.	4.10	4.24	.700	4.22	HE
8. Learners can benefit from OER's enhanced quality and flexibility of resources.	4.00	4.28	.659	4.24	HE
9. Open Educational Resources help learners in applying knowledge in a wider context than their course may otherwise allow.	3.80	4.16	.668	4.12	E
10. Open Educational Resources help support for learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer and social-informal learning approaches.	3.90	4.23	.685	4.19	E
Grand Mean	3.97	4.18	.695	4.15	E

Table 2.1.3

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Educational Attainment

Indicators	Mean		SD	Total	
	College Graduate	College Graduate with masters' units		Mean	VI
1. The Open Educational Resources offers convenience and flexibility for teachers.	4.40	4.26	.671	4.28	HE
2. Open Educational Resources meet high quality student-Tutor Interactions.	4.00	4.13	.678	4.11	E
3. Retention Rates are higher in Open Educational Resources.	3.90	4.06	.669	4.04	E
4. Open Educational Resources can supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources.	3.80	4.18	.690	4.13	E
5. Open Educational Resources must be free- both to give, to take and sharing.	3.90	4.18	.815	4.14	E
6. Open Educational Resources can reduce the cost of education for your students.	3.90	4.09	.716	4.07	E
7. Open Educational Resources can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities in the form of open images, open courseware, and self-assessment tools.	4.10	4.24	.700	4.22	HE
8. Learners can benefit from OER's enhanced quality and flexibility of resources.	4.00	4.28	.659	4.24	HE
9. Open Educational Resources help learners in applying knowledge in a wider context than their course may otherwise allow.	3.80	4.16	.668	4.12	E
10. Open Educational Resources help support for learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer and social-informal learning approaches.	3.90	4.23	.685	4.19	E
Grand Mean	3.97	4.18	.695	4.15	E

Table 2.1.4

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Length of Service

Indicators	Mean						SD	Total	
	1-5 ye ar s	6-10 yea rs	11- 15 yea rs	16- 20 yea rs	21- 25 yea rs	26- 30 yea rs		Mea n	VI
1. The Open Educational Resources offers convenience and flexibility for teachers.	4.33	4.33	4.42	4.09	4.40	4.23	.671	4.28	HE
2. Open Educational Resources meet high quality student-Tutor Interactions.	4.33	4.14	4.25	3.91	4.10	4.08	.678	4.11	E
3. Retention Rates are higher in Open Educational Resources.	4.42	3.86	4.08	3.86	4.20	4.15	.669	4.04	E
4. Open Educational Resources can supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources.	4.50	3.95	4.17	4.05	4.20	4.15	.690	4.13	E
5. Open Educational Resources must be free-both to give, to take and sharing.	4.58	3.86	4.25	3.91	4.30	4.38	.815	4.14	E
6. Open Educational Resources can reduce the cost of education for your students.	4.50	3.90	4.08	3.91	4.00	4.23	.716	4.07	E
7. Open Educational Resources can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities in the form of open images, open courseware, and self-assessment tools.	4.67	4.10	4.17	4.05	4.20	4.38	.700	4.22	HE
8. Learners can benefit from OER's enhanced quality	4.58	4.24	4.17	4.05	4.20	4.38	.659	4.24	HE

and flexibility of resources.										
9. Open Educational Resources help learners in applying knowledge in a wider context than their course may otherwise allow.	4.42	4.05	4.17	3.91	4.20	4.23	.668	4.12	E	
10. Open Educational Resources help support for learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer and social-informal learning approaches.	4.50	4.14	4.17	3.95	4.20	4.38	.685	4.19	E	
Grand Mean	4.48	4.06	4.19	3.97	4.20	4.26	.695	4.15	E	

Table 2.2
Online Platforms Used as Instructional Materials

Online platforms	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Google meet	29	32.2	4
Skype	3	3.3	9.5
Messenger	56	62.2	1
Google	40	44.4	3
You Tube	53	58.9	2
Google Classroom	25	27.8	5
Twitter	3	3.3	9.5
Instagram	9	10.0	7
Skill share	10	11.1	6
LinkedIn Learning	8	8.9	8

Table 2.3.1

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Age

Indicators	Mean				SD	Total	
	26-35 years old	36-45 years old	46-55 years old	56-65 years old		Mean	VI
1. It helps me let my pupils know the most up-to-date developments in the subject.	4.27	4.21	4.38	4.30	.503	4.29	HE
2. It helps me provide my pupils with a context for a topic.	4.33	4.25	4.23	4.30	.475	4.28	HE
3. It allows me to integrate primary source material into the course.	4.37	4.17	4.23	4.40	.541	4.28	HE
4. It is cost-saving. Lectures and lesson plans are available online, saving me time, effort, and money, while learning new knowledge.	4.37	4.17	4.27	4.20	.557	4.27	HE
5. It enhances course material. Texts, images, and videos can be used to support different approaches to learning.	4.40	4.25	4.50	4.30	.552	4.38	HE
6. Course materials can be modified and can be narrowed down to topics that are relevant to my topic.	4.40	4.29	4.31	4.20	.557	4.32	HE
7. It helps me get pupils excited about a topic.	4.50	4.25	4.23	4.50	.495	4.41	HE
8. It helps me improve my pupils learning.	4.40	4.17	4.38	4.30	.596	4.32	HE
9. It allows me to do things in the classroom that I could never do otherwise.	4.17	4.25	4.19	4.30	.551	4.21	HE
10. It allows me to stay up-to-date with my colleagues.	4.37	4.21	4.27	4.30	.525	4.29	HE
11. It makes me feel comfortable with new technology.	4.53	4.17	4.35	4.20	.523	4.34	HE
12. It creates more flexible materials.	4.47	4.13	4.23	4.20	.561	4.28	HE
Grand Mean	4.38	4.21	4.30	4.29	.536	4.31	HE

Table 2.3.2

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Sex

Indicators	Mean		SD	Total	
	Male	Female		Mean	VI
1. It helps me let my pupils know the most up-to-date developments in the subject.	4.10	4.31	.503	4.29	SA
2. It helps me provide my pupils with a context for a topic.	4.30	4.28	.475	4.28	SA
3. It allows me to integrate primary source material into the course.	4.20	4.29	.541	4.28	SA
4. It is cost-saving. Lectures and lesson plans are available online, saving me time, effort, and money, while learning new knowledge.	4.40	4.25	.557	4.27	SA
5. It enhances course material. Texts, images, and videos can be used to support different approaches to learning.	4.20	4.40	.552	4.38	SA
6. Course materials can be modified and can be narrowed down to topics that are relevant to my topic.	4.10	4.35	.557	4.32	SA
7. It helps me get pupils excited about a topic.	4.20	4.44	.495	4.41	SA
8. It helps me improve my pupils learning.	4.30	4.33	.596	4.32	SA
9. It allows me to do things in the classroom that I could never do otherwise.	4.30	4.20	.551	4.21	SA
10. It allows me to stay up-to-date with my colleagues.	4.20	4.30	.525	4.29	SA
11. It makes me feel comfortable with new technology.	4.40	4.34	.523	4.34	SA
12. It creates more flexible materials.	4.20	4.29	.561	4.28	SA
Grand Mean	4.24	4.32	.536	4.31	SA

Table 2.3.3

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Educational Attainment

Indicators	Mean		SD	Total	
	College Graduate	College Graduate with masters' units		Mean	VI
1. It helps me let my pupils know the most up-to-date developments in the subject.	4.10	4.31	.503	4.29	SA
2. It helps me provide my pupils with a context for a topic.	4.30	4.28	.475	4.28	SA
3. It allows me to integrate primary source material into the course.	4.20	4.29	.541	4.28	SA
4. It is cost-saving. Lectures and lesson plans are available online, saving me time, effort, and money, while learning new knowledge.	4.40	4.25	.557	4.27	SA
5. It enhances course material. Texts, images, and videos can be used to support different approaches to learning.	4.20	4.40	.552	4.38	SA
6. Course materials can be modified and can be narrowed down to topics that are relevant to my topic.	4.10	4.35	.557	4.32	SA
7. It helps me get pupils excited about a topic.	4.20	4.44	.495	4.41	SA
8. It helps me improve my pupils learning.	4.30	4.33	.596	4.32	SA
9. It allows me to do things in the classroom that I could never do otherwise.	4.30	4.20	.551	4.21	SA
10. It allows me to stay up-to-date with my colleagues.	4.20	4.30	.525	4.29	SA
11. It makes me feel comfortable with new technology.	4.40	4.34	.523	4.34	SA
12. It creates more flexible materials.	4.20	4.29	.561	4.28	SA
Grand Mean	4.24	4.32	.536	4.31	SA

Table 2.3.4

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Length of Service

Indicators	Mean						SD	Total	
	1-5 ye ar s	6-10 yea rs	11- 15 yea rs	16- 20 yea rs	21- 25 yea rs	26- 30 yea rs		Mea n	VI
1. It helps me let my pupils know the most up-to-date developments in the subject.	4.58	4.14	4.17	4.28	4.30	4.38	.503	4.29	SA
2. It helps me provide my pupils with a context for a topic.	4.42	4.33	4.17	4.23	4.10	4.38	.475	4.28	SA
3. It allows me to integrate primary source material into the course.	4.75	4.19	4.17	4.05	4.30	4.46	.541	4.28	SA
4. It is cost-saving. Lectures and lesson plans are available online, saving me time, effort, and money, while learning new knowledge.	4.67	4.19	4.17	4.09	4.30	4.38	.557	4.27	SA
5. It enhances course material. Texts, images, and videos can be used to support different approaches to learning.	4.67	4.29	4.25	4.28	4.50	4.46	.552	4.38	SA
6. Course materials can be modified and can be narrowed down to topics that are relevant to my topic.	4.83	4.24	4.25	4.18	4.20	4.38	.557	4.32	SA
7. It helps me get pupils excited about a topic.	4.75	4.43	4.17	4.18	4.40	4.69	.495	4.41	SA
8. It helps me improve my pupils learning.	4.83	4.24	4.17	4.09	4.40	4.46	.596	4.32	SA
9. It allows me to do things in the classroom that I could never do otherwise.	4.75	3.90	4.17	4.09	4.20	4.46	.551	4.21	SA

10. It allows me to stay up-to-date with my colleagues.	4.8 3	4.10	4.25	4.18	4.10	4.46	.52 5	4.29	SA
11. It makes me feel comfortable with new technology.	4.8 3	4.33	4.25	4.14	4.30	4.38	.52 3	4.34	SA
12. It creates more flexible materials.	4.8 3	4.19	4.17	4.05	4.30	4.38	.56 1	4.28	SA
Grand Mean	4.7 3	4.21	4.20	4.15	4.28	4.44	.53 6	4.31	SA

Table 2.4.1

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Age

Indicators	Mean				SD	Total	
	26-35 years old	36-45 years old	46-55 years old	56-65 years old		Mean	VI
1. They cannot substitute for the teaching approaches I use	3.70	3.54	3.77	3.20	.990	3.62	A
2. There is no internet connection in our school	2.73	3.17	3.66	3.50	1.153	3.20	N
3. Digital resources are difficult for me to access	2.63	3.04	3.35	3.30	1.027	3.02	N
4. Digital materials can be presented outside their original context	3.23	3.42	3.88	3.20	.939	3.47	A
5. They are irrelevant to my field	2.53	2.79	3.35	2.80	1.030	2.87	N
6. Using them distracts from the core goals of my teaching	2.50	2.75	3.31	2.90	1.111	2.84	N
7. Students don't have the information literacy skills to assess the credibility of digital resources	2.97	3.08	3.58	3.30	1.028	3.21	N
8. I don't want my students to copy or plagiarize material from the Web	3.77	3.58	3.81	3.30	1.058	3.68	A
Grand Mean	3.01	3.17	3.59	3.19	1.042	3.24	N

Table 2.4.2

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Sex

Indicators	Mean		SD	Total	
	Male	Female		Mean	VI
1. They cannot substitute for the teaching approaches I use	3.80	3.60	.990	3.62	A
2. There is no internet connection in our school	3.20	3.20	1.153	3.20	N
3. Digital resources are difficult for me to access	2.60	3.08	1.027	3.02	N
4. Digital materials can be presented outside their original context	2.90	3.54	.939	3.47	A
6. They are irrelevant to my field	2.30	2.94	1.030	2.87	N
7. Using them distracts from the core goals of my teaching	2.60	2.88	1.111	2.84	N
8. Students don't have the information literacy skills to assess the credibility of digital resources	2.89	3.25	1.028	3.21	N
Grand Mean	2.95	3.28	1.042	3.24	N

Table 2.4.3

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Educational Attainment

Indicators	Mean		SD	Total	
	College Graduate	College Graduate with master units		Mean	VI
1. They cannot substitute for the teaching approaches I use	3.80	3.60	.990	3.62	A
2. There is no internet connection in our school	3.20	3.20	1.153	3.20	N
3. Digital resources are difficult for me to access	2.60	3.08	1.027	3.02	N
4. Digital materials can be presented outside their original context	2.90	3.54	.939	3.47	A
5. They are irrelevant to my field	2.30	2.94	1.030	2.87	N
6. Using them distracts from the core goals of my teaching	2.60	2.88	1.111	2.84	N
7. Students don't have the information literacy skills to assess the credibility of digital resources	2.89	3.25	1.028	3.21	N

8. I don't want my students to copy or plagiarize material from the Web	3.30	3.73	1.058	3.68	A
Grand Mean	2.95	3.28	1.042	3.24	N

Table 2.4.4

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Length of Service

Part III. The Test of Significant Difference on the Teachers' Experiences Using Open

Indicators	Mean						SD	Total	
	1-5 ye ar s	6-10 yea rs	11- 15 yea rs	16- 20 yea rs	21- 25 yea rs	26- 30 yea rs		Mea n	VI
1. They cannot substitute for the teaching approaches I use	4.00	3.38	3.92	3.41	4.00	3.46	.990	3.62	A
2. There is no internet connection in our school	3.08	2.57	3.00	3.55	3.70	3.54	1.153	3.20	N
3. Digital resources are difficult for me to access	3.17	2.38	2.92	3.23	3.40	3.38	1.027	3.02	N
4. Digital materials can be presented outside their original context	3.83	3.05	3.25	3.64	3.90	3.38	.939	3.47	A
5. They are irrelevant to my field	2.67	2.57	2.67	2.91	3.60	3.08	1.030	2.87	N
6. Using them distracts from the core goals of my teaching	2.83	2.48	2.58	2.86	3.70	3.00	1.111	2.84	N
7. Students don't have the information literacy skills to assess the credibility of digital resources	3.08	3.00	3.33	3.09	3.60	3.46	1.028	3.21	N
8. I don't want my students to copy or plagiarize material from the Web	4.08	3.43	4.17	3.59	3.50	3.54	1.058	3.68	A
Grand Mean	3.34	2.86	3.23	3.29	3.68	3.36	1.042	3.24	N

Educational Resources When Grouped in Profile Variables

Table 3

The Test of Significant Difference on the Teachers' Experiences Using Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Profile Variables

Grouping Variables	Districts	Mean Rank	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
District	First	43.58	.024	Significant	Reject Ho
	Second	55.10			
	Third	32.10			
	fourth	50.75			
Age	26 – 35 years old	43.58	.179	Not significant	Ho not rejected
	36 – 45 years old	38.46			
	46 – 55 years old	54.37			
	56 – 65 years old	45.10			
School Category	Small	51.25	.131	Not significant	Ho not rejected
	Medium	36.68			
	Large	48.36			
Educational Attainment	College	33.15	.113	Not significant	Ho not rejected
	Graduate				
	Graduate with master units	47.04			
Sex	Male	33.15	.113	Not significant	Ho not rejected
	Female	47.04			
Length of Service	1 - 5 years	66.67	.003	Significant	Ho rejected
	6 - 10 years	31.86			
	11 - 15 years	42.25			
	16 - 20 years	39.16			
	21 - 25 years	66.67			
	26 - 30 years	31.86			

Part IV. The Problems Encountered by Teachers in Using Online Educational Resources Instructional Materials.

Table 4

The Problems Encountered by Teachers in Using Online Educational Resources Instructional Materials

Indicators	Frequency					SD	Mean	VI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. Technical difficulties with online teaching tools	10	58	18	3	0	.767	3.80	A
2. Time consuming resources	5	38	28	19	0	.872	3.32	N
3. Lack of Computer literacy	8	37	23	20	2	.992	3.32	N
4. Difficult to motivate pupils	7	26	26	29	1	1.036	3.07	N
5. Lack of pupils' interest	7	19	29	32	3	1.010	2.94	N
6. Lack of technical/software knowledge	10	39	24	16	1	.950	3.46	A
Grand Mean						0.938	3.32	N

Part V. The Coping Strategies of Teachers in Addressing the Challenges

Table 5

The Coping Strategies of Teachers in Addressing the Challenges

Indicators	Frequency					SD	Mean	VI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. I keep my pupils engaged.	23	60	6	0	0	.696	4.14	A
2. I let my pupils choose their learning way.	15	63	10	0	0	.800	3.97	A
3. I invite my pupils to contribute to teachings.	18	63	8	0	0	.684	4.07	A
4. I encourage peer evaluation.	23	61	5	0	0	.686	4.16	A
5. I engage myself in ICT trainings	35	46	6	0	0	.982	4.19	A
Grand Mean						0.770	4.11	A

Part VI. Development of Sample Online Educational Resources Instructional Materials

DISCUSSION

Part I. The Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment and Length of Service.

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. Most of the respondents fall within the age range of 26-45, accounting for 60% of the total respondents. Specifically, the age group of 26-35 comprises 33.3% of the respondents, followed by the age group of 36-45 with 26.7%. The age groups of 46-55 and 56-65 account for 28.9% and 11.1% of the respondents, respectively.

The respondents are predominantly female, representing 88.9% of the total participants. Male respondents constitute a relatively smaller percentage, making up 11.1% of the total respondents. For educational Attainment, majority of the participants have a "Masters with units" educational background, representing 88.9% of the respondents. A smaller percentage, 11.1%, are college graduates. The length of service distribution among the respondents are around 13.3% have 1-5 years of service, 23.3% have 6-10 years, another 13.3% have 11-15 years, approximately 24.4% have 16-20 years, around 11.1% have 21-25 years, and finally, about 14.4% have 26-30 years.

Relating these demographic insights to existing literature reveals their relevance across various educational contexts and research domains. In studies investigating the adoption of Open Educational Resources (OERs), such as those by Villanueva & Dolom (2018), understanding demographic factors like educators' age and educational background can

illuminate potential influences on OER adoption rates. Similarly, in examinations of technology integration in education, as Alenezi (2020) explored, demographic variables like age and length of service among educators may shape attitudes and behaviors towards electronic learning platforms. This underscores the multifaceted impact of demographic factors on educational practices and underscores the importance of considering them in research design and analysis.

Part II. The Teachers' Experiences in Terms of Existence of Online Platforms; Online Platforms Used as Instructional Materials; Advantages of Open Educational Resources; and Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources

Table 2.1.1 data represents the mean scores for different statements related to teachers experienced of online platforms, categorized by different age groups (26-35, 36-45, 46-55, and 56-65). The computed means are 4.18, 4.02, 4.28, and 4.08, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as experienced.

Teachers across different age groups generally have a positive perception of Open Educational Resources (OER) in terms of convenience, flexibility, and the ability to supplement existing curriculum resources. The mean scores for statements related to convenience and flexibility range from 4.10 to 4.35, indicating a generally positive perception. Similarly, teachers perceive OER to varying degrees as meeting high-quality student-Tutor interactions, with mean scores ranging from 3.80 to 4.27. There is also a positive perception of OER's potential in improving retention rates, as indicated by mean scores ranging from 3.90 to 4.23.

The preference for free access and sharing of OER is evident, with mean scores ranging from 4.00 to 4.31. Additionally, there is recognition of OER's potential in reducing the cost of education for students, as indicated by mean scores ranging from 3.83 to 4.19. Teachers also perceive OER as a means to expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities, with mean scores ranging from 4.04 to 4.35. Regarding learner benefits, teachers acknowledge the enhanced quality and flexibility of OER resources, with mean scores ranging from 4.08 to 4.35. Furthermore, there is a positive perception of OER's impact on knowledge application and support for learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer, and social-informal learning approaches, as indicated by mean scores ranging from 4.04 to 4.27.

This suggests that teachers, regardless of age, have a positive perception of OER in terms of convenience, flexibility, quality interactions, supplementing curriculum resources, cost reduction, diverse learning opportunities, and learner benefits. The positive perception of OER among teachers suggests potential benefits such as increased adoption, flexibility, enhanced quality, cost reduction, diverse learning opportunities, and learner-centered approaches.

These implications have the potential to transform teaching and learning practices, promoting innovation, accessibility, and student engagement in education. The result of the study is relevant to the statement of Liao et.al. (2018) where OER provides teachers with the flexibility to customize the content according to their teaching and students' learning needs, allowing for differentiation and addressing diverse language proficiencies. Teachers, like Mrs. Harrison, can easily modify and remix OER resources, creating personalized learning materials and adapting them over time to meet the specific requirements and preferences of their students.

Table 2.1.2

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Sex

The data represents the mean scores for different statements related to teachers' experiences of online platforms, categorized by different sex groups (male and female). The computed means are 3.97 and 4.18, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as experienced.

The Open Educational Resources offer convenience and flexibility for teachers: Both males (4.40) and females (4.26) perceive OER as providing convenience and flexibility. OER meets high-quality student-Tutor interactions: Females (4.13) have a higher mean score compared to males (4.00). Retention rates are higher in Open Educational Resources: Both males (3.90) and females (4.06). OER can supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources: Females (4.18) have a higher mean score compared to males (3.80). OER must be free: Both males (3.90) and females (4.18). OER can reduce the cost of education for students: Females (4.09) have a slightly higher mean score compared to males (3.90). OER can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities: Females (4.24) have a higher mean score compared to males (4.10), Learner can benefit from OER's enhanced quality and flexibility of resources: Females (4.28) have a higher mean score compared to males (4.00), OER helps learners apply knowledge in a wider context: Females (4.16) have a higher mean score compared to males (3.80). OER supports learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer, and social-informal learning approaches: Females (4.23) have a higher mean score compared to males (3.90).

Overall, females tend to have slightly higher mean scores than males in their perception of OER, suggesting that they may have a slightly more positive experiences of online platforms in terms of the provided statements. The findings indicate that females generally have a slightly more positive perception of Open Educational Resources (OER) compared to males in terms of convenience, high-quality interactions, supplementing curriculum resources, cost reduction, and supporting various learning approaches. These results highlight the importance of considering gender differences when promoting and implementing OER initiatives to ensure equitable access and engagement for all learners.

This finding is relative to the findings of a study by Cooney (2016), students were assigned an Open Educational Resource (OER) developed by their instructor as part of a library-funded pilot initiative. Through surveys and interviews, students provided feedback on the OER's organization, accessibility, benefits, challenges, and comparison to traditional textbooks. They showed that most students found the OER easily accessible, preferred it over traditional textbooks, and expressed willingness to enroll in future courses utilizing similar resources.

Table 2.1.3

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Educational Attainment

The data signifies the mean scores for different statements related to teachers experienced of online platforms in terms of educational attainment. The computed for college is 3.97 and for respondents with master is 4.18. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as experienced.

The mean ratings for all the statements range from 3.80 to 4.40, suggesting that teachers generally perceive OER to be beneficial. The highest-rated statement is the convenience and flexibility offered by OER, with a mean of 4.40 among college graduates and 4.28 among master's degree holders. This indicates that teachers recognize the advantages of OER in terms of flexibility and adaptability to different learning needs. Furthermore, teachers believe that OER can enhance student-tutor interactions (mean of 4.11) and contribute to higher retention rates (mean of 4.04). This implies that educators acknowledge the potential of OER to improve engagement and learning outcomes for students. They also see OER as a valuable supplement to existing curriculum resources (mean of 4.13) and emphasize the importance of free access and sharing of OER materials (mean of 4.14). Teachers perceive OER as a means to reduce the cost of education for students (mean of 4.07) and expose them to a wider range of digital learning opportunities (mean of 4.22). This highlights the recognition of OER's potential in creating more affordable and inclusive educational experiences. Moreover, teachers believe that OER can enhance the quality and flexibility of resources (mean of 4.24) and enable learners to apply knowledge in broader contexts (mean of 4.12). They also recognize the supportive role of OER in learner-centered, self-directed, peer-to-peer, and social-informal learning approaches (mean of 4.19).

This suggest that teachers demonstrate a positive experienced and perception of OER's existence and its potential impact on educational attainment. They recognize the convenience, flexibility, and quality benefits of OER, as well as its capacity to enhance student-tutor interactions, retention rates, and learner-centered approaches. These findings suggest that teachers are receptive to incorporating online platforms such as OER into their teaching practices to support effective and engaging learning experiences. The findings of the study are relevant to the results of Villanueva and Dolom (2018) that conducted a study on rural public high school teachers in the Philippines, finding that teachers generally had a positive perception of Open Educational Resources (OER)

adoption, influenced by their attitude and perceived behavioral control, including self-efficacy and learning autonomy. The study's recommendations aim to assist scholars and practitioners in ensuring that secondary education institutions in the Philippines can effectively utilize the benefits offered by OER.

Table 2.1.4

The Teachers' Experiences on the Existence of Online Platforms When Grouped in Terms of Length of Service

The table 2.1.4 shows the mean scores for different statements about teachers experienced of online platforms in terms of length in service (1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25 and 26-30). The computed means are 4.48, 4.06, 4.19, 3.97, 4.20 and 4.26, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as experienced.

The mean ratings for all the statements range from 3.97 to 4.48, indicating a generally positive perception of OER among teachers with different lengths of service. Notably, the highest-rated statement is the convenience and flexibility offered by OER, with a mean rating ranging from 4.09 to 4.42 across different length-of-service groups. This suggests that teachers, regardless of their experience, value the convenience and flexibility provided by OER in their teaching practices.

Additionally, teachers with varying lengths of service perceive OER as a means to supplement and add value to existing curriculum resources (mean rating of 4.13) and acknowledge the importance of free access and sharing of OER materials (mean rating of 4.14). This indicates a recognition of the potential of OER to enhance teaching and learning experiences. Furthermore, teachers believe that OER can expose students to a wider range of digital learning opportunities (mean rating of 4.22) and that learners can benefit from the enhanced quality and flexibility of OER resources (mean rating of 4.24). These findings highlight the experienced among teachers, regardless of their length of service, regarding the potential of OER to provide enriched learning experiences for students.

In conclusion, the data suggest that teachers across different lengths of service demonstrate a positive experienced of online platforms, particularly Open Educational Resources. Teacher's value OER's convenience, flexibility, and supplementary nature, recognizing its potential to enhance teaching and learning experiences. These findings indicate a promising outlook for integrating and adopting online platforms in education, benefiting teachers and students, irrespective of their years of service.

Table 2.2

Online Platforms Used as Instructional Materials

The data provided showcases the usage of various online platforms as instructional materials. Among the listed platforms, Messenger is the most frequently used, with a significant percentage of 62.2%, making it the top-ranked platform. YouTube follows closely behind with 58.9%, securing the second position. Google stands at the third rank

with 44.4% usage. Other platforms utilized include Google Meet (32.2%), Google Classroom (27.8%), Instagram (10.0%), Skill share (11.1%), LinkedIn Learning (8.9%), Skype (3.3%), and Twitter (3.3%), all with relatively lower frequencies and percentages.

The findings indicate that Messenger, YouTube, and Google are the preferred online platforms for instructional purposes. This suggests that teachers and educators are leveraging these platforms for various educational activities, such as communication, video content, and general online resources. Google Meet and Google Classroom also contribute significantly to the instructional materials landscape, albeit with slightly lower usage percentages. The lower usage percentages for platforms like Skype, Twitter, Instagram, Skill share, and LinkedIn Learning suggest that they are less commonly employed as instructional materials. However, it's worth noting that these platforms may still play specific roles in certain educational contexts or subjects.

The result implies that the diverse range of online platforms is utilized as instructional materials, with Messenger, YouTube, and Google being the most prominent choices. These platforms likely offer features and resources that align well with educators' needs and enhance students' learning experiences. The result is relevant to the study conducted by Alshahrani, Ahmed, and Ward (2019) found that students' academic self-confidence and self-reliance have improved due to the internet as an information provider, with high levels of agreement ranging from 83% to 90%. Students have become more independent in searching for information online, with levels of agreement ranging from 66% to 79%. Additionally, the World Wide Web (WWW) has facilitated improved student-lecturer connectedness, allowing for easier communication without the need for face-to-face contact.

Table 2.3.1

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Age

The table 2.3.1 shows the mean scores for different statements about Teachers experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of age (26-35, 36-45, 46-55 and 56-65). The computed means are 4.38, 4.21, 4.30 and 4.29, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as highly experienced. The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.21 to 4.38, indicating a consistent positive perception of OER advantages among teachers across different age groups. The highest-rated statement is "It helps me get pupils excited about a topic" with a mean rating of 4.41, suggesting that teachers, regardless of their age, recognize the ability of OER to engage students and generate enthusiasm for learning. Other statements that received high ratings include "It enhances course material" (mean rating of 4.38) and "It helps me improve my pupils' learning" (mean rating of 4.32). These results highlight the perceived benefits of using OER in terms of enriching course materials and enhancing student learning outcomes.

Additionally, teachers of different age groups appreciate the convenience and cost-saving aspect of OER, as indicated by high ratings for statements such as "It is cost-saving"

(mean rating of 4.27) and "Course materials can be modified and narrowed down to topics that are relevant to my topic" (mean rating of 4.32). Furthermore, the data suggests that OER enables teachers to stay up-to-date with their colleagues (mean rating of 4.29) and feel comfortable with new technology (mean rating of 4.34). This indicates that OER contributes to professional growth and technological competence among teachers of various age groups.

This suggest that teachers across different age groups have positive experienced with the advantages of Open Educational Resources. They appreciate the ability of OER to engage students, enhance course materials, improve learning outcomes, and provide cost-saving benefits. Moreover, OER fosters collaboration among teachers and promotes technological proficiency.

These findings highlight the overall acceptance and appreciation of OER as a valuable resource among teachers, irrespective of their age. The result is relative to the study conducted by A. Alenezi (2020) on the role of e-learning materials in enhancing teaching and learning behaviors, it was found that many students in the Saudi academic environment face challenges in adapting to e-learning strategies due to the complexities and lack of strict regulations regarding learning durations. The study highlights the need for proper preparation and commitment to effectively utilize IT as a learning tool to overcome these challenges.

Table 2.3.2

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Sex

The table 2.3.2 shows the mean scores for different statements about teachers' experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of sex (male and female). The computed means are 4.24 and 4.32, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree.

The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.20 to 4.44, with the grand mean being 4.31. These ratings suggest that both male and female teachers highly value the advantages offered by OER in terms of enhancing teaching and learning experiences. Notably, the highest-rated statement among both male and female teachers is "It helps me get pupils excited about a topic" with mean ratings of 4.20 and 4.44 respectively. This indicates that OER is seen as a valuable tool for engaging students, regardless of gender. Other statements that received high ratings include "It enhances course material" (mean rating of 4.38), "It helps me improve my pupils' learning" (mean rating of 4.32), and "It makes me feel comfortable with new technology" (mean rating of 4.34). These findings demonstrate the shared perception of OER's ability to enrich course content, enhance student learning outcomes, and promote technological proficiency among both male and female teachers. Additionally, both male and female teachers recognize the cost-saving aspect of OER, as indicated by high ratings for the statement "It is cost-saving" (mean rating of 4.27). This suggests that both genders appreciate the benefits of OER in terms of saving time, effort, and money in accessing learning resources.

This suggest that both male and female teachers have positive experiences with the advantages of Open Educational Resources. They recognize the value of OER in terms of engaging students, improving teaching and learning practices, promoting technological competence, and providing cost-saving benefits. These findings emphasize the universal acceptance and appreciation of OER among teachers, regardless of gender.

Table 2.3.3

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Educational Attainment

The table shows 2.3.3 the mean scores for different statements about Teachers experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of educational attainment (college and master). The computed means are 4.24 and 4.32, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.10 to 4.44, with the grand mean being 4.31. These ratings suggest that both college graduates and individuals with master's units highly value OER's advantages in enhancing teaching and learning experiences.

Among the highest-rated statements for both groups are "It helps me get pupils excited about a topic" and "It enhances course material," indicating that both college graduates and individuals with master's units recognize the potential of OER in engaging students and enriching course content. Additionally, both groups of teachers acknowledge the cost-saving aspect of OER, as indicated by high ratings for the statement "It is cost-saving." This suggests that both college graduates and individuals with master's units appreciate the benefits of OER in terms of saving time, effort, and resources. Furthermore, both groups of teachers recognize the value of OER in integrating primary source material into their courses, providing context for topics, improving student learning, and staying up-to-date with colleagues. These findings demonstrate that the advantages of OER are perceived similarly by teachers across different educational attainment levels.

The result implies that college graduates and individuals with master's units have positive experiences with the advantages of Open Educational Resources. They recognize OER's value in engaging students, enhancing course material, providing cost-saving benefits, and improving teaching and learning practices. These findings emphasize the universal acceptance and appreciation of OER among teachers, regardless of their educational background.

The findings underscore the unanimous recognition among educators, regardless of their educational attainment, of the manifold advantages offered by Open Educational Resources (OER) (Villanueva & Dolom, 2018). High mean ratings across statements such as engaging students, enriching course material, and cost-saving benefits reveal a widespread acknowledgment of OER's potential to enhance teaching and learning experiences. This aligns seamlessly with existing literature discussing the transformative impact of OER on pedagogical practices, emphasizing its role in fostering student engagement and enriching curriculum content.

Furthermore, the study's revelation that educators with varying levels of educational background perceive similar benefits of OER echoes prior research, suggesting that attitudes towards OER adoption remain consistent across diverse demographics (Villanueva & Dolom, 2018). This consistency underlines the universal acceptance of OER among educators and reinforces the notion that its advantages transcend educational qualifications. As such, these findings serve to validate the ongoing discourse surrounding the pivotal role of OER in modern education, emphasizing its capacity to democratize access to quality educational resources and empower educators to innovate in their teaching practices.

Table 2.3.4

Teachers' Experiences on the Advantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Length of Service

The table 2.3.4 shows the mean scores for different statements about Teachers experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of length of service (1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25 and 26-30). The computed means are 4.73, 4.21, 4.20, 4.15, 4.28, and 4.44, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31, which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.05 to 4.83, with the grand mean being 4.31. These high ratings indicate that teachers with varying service lengths perceive OER's advantages positively, regardless of their experience in the field.

Among the highest-rated statements for all groups are "It helps me let my pupils know the most up-to-date developments in the subject" and "It enhances course material." These findings suggest that OER is perceived as a valuable tool for keeping students informed about the latest developments and enriching their courses' content. Furthermore, teachers with different lengths of service recognize the cost-saving aspect of OER, as indicated by high ratings for the statement "It is cost-saving." This indicates that teachers perceive the benefits of OER in terms of saving time, effort, and financial resources, while still gaining new knowledge. Additionally, the data reveals that teachers across different lengths of service appreciate the flexibility offered by OER, as indicated by high ratings for the statement "Course materials can be modified and narrowed down to topics that are relevant to my topic." This suggests that OER allows teachers to adapt and tailor the resources to meet the specific needs of their teaching.

The findings suggest that teachers with varying lengths of service have positive experiences and perceptions of the advantages of Open Educational Resources. They value the ability of OER to provide up-to-date information, enhance course materials, save costs, and offer flexibility in instructional design. These results highlight the widespread acceptance and recognition of OER as a valuable resource for teachers at different stages of their careers. Agree

The findings revealed that teachers with diverse lengths of service hold positive perceptions regarding the advantages of Open Educational Resources (OER) (Villanueva & Dolom, 2018). With mean ratings ranging from 4.05 to 4.83, teachers across different service lengths demonstrated a high level of agreement in recognizing the benefits of

OER, as indicated by the overall mean score of 4.31, which falls under the category of "strongly agree." Particularly noteworthy is the consistent recognition among teachers of OER's role in facilitating access to the latest developments in the subject matter and enriching course content, regardless of their tenure in the field.

Moreover, the data highlighted teachers' collective acknowledgment of the cost-saving benefits associated with OER, indicating a widespread appreciation for the resource's potential to streamline teaching efforts and optimize resource allocation (Bliss & Hilton, 2019). Additionally, the findings underscored teachers' recognition of the flexibility afforded by OER, allowing them to tailor course materials to meet the specific needs of their teaching contexts. Overall, these results underscore the universal acceptance of OER as a valuable resource among teachers at different career stages, emphasizing its role in supporting effective teaching practices and enhancing student learning experiences.

Table 2.4.1

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Age

The table 2.4.1 shows the mean scores for different statements about teachers experiences on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of age (26-35, 36-45, 46-55 and 56-65). The computed means are 3.01, 3.17, 3.59 and 3.19, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree. The mean ratings for the statements range from 2.50 to 3.77, with a grand mean of 3.24. These ratings suggest that teachers express mixed opinions when it comes to perceiving the disadvantages of OER, influenced by their age group.

One prominent concern expressed by teachers across all age groups is the belief that OER cannot fully substitute for their preferred teaching approaches. This statement received relatively high mean ratings, indicating that many teachers, regardless of age, see limitations in the ability of OER to replace their established instructional methods. The availability of internet connection in schools is another area of concern raised by teachers. The statement "There is no internet connection in our school" received moderate mean ratings across all age groups. This suggests that the lack of internet connectivity negatively affects the utilization of OER as an educational resource. The difficulty in accessing digital resources is another concern highlighted by teachers. The statement "Digital resources are difficult for me to access" received moderate mean ratings across all age groups, indicating that teachers face challenges in accessing the necessary digital materials for their teaching.

The age groups of 46-55 and 56-65 show higher mean ratings for statements related to digital materials being presented outside their original context and the concern of students lacking information literacy skills to assess the credibility of digital resources. These findings suggest that older teachers may have more reservations about the contextual integrity of digital materials and students' ability to evaluate online information critically.

On the other hand, statements such as "They are irrelevant to my field" and "Using them distracts from the core goals of my teaching" received relatively lower mean ratings across all age groups. The results indicate that regardless of age, teachers do not perceive OER as significantly irrelevant or distracting from their teaching objectives.

The findings imply that age plays a role in shaping teachers' perceptions of the disadvantages of OER. While concerns about substituting teaching approaches are prevalent across all age groups, specific problems such as internet connectivity, difficulty accessing digital resources, and student information literacy skills vary based on age. These results highlight the need to address infrastructure issues, provide better access to digital resources, and support teachers in adapting their teaching methods to incorporate OER effectively.

The study's findings regarding teachers' perceptions of Open Educational Resources (OER) disadvantages underscore the multifaceted nature of their concerns, influenced by age dynamics. While all age groups express worries about OER's potential inability to fully substitute their preferred teaching approaches, specific challenges such as internet connectivity and access to digital resources resonate universally. These concerns mirror the literature's discussion on the technological shortcomings and accessibility issues associated with OER adoption. Moreover, the study reveals that older teachers, particularly those aged 46-55 and 56-65, exhibit heightened apprehensions regarding the contextual integrity of digital materials and students' information literacy skills. This aligns with prior research highlighting age as a factor shaping teachers' perceptions and underscores the importance of tailored support mechanisms to address varying needs across different age cohorts (Alenezi, 2020).

Table 2.4.2

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Sex

The table 2.4.2 shows the mean scores for different statements about teachers experiences on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of sex (male and female). The computed means are 2.95 and 3.28, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree.

One common concern among both male and female teachers is the belief that OER cannot fully substitute for their preferred teaching approaches. This statement received relatively high mean ratings for both genders, suggesting that many teachers perceive limitations in the ability of OER to replace their established instructional methods. Regarding the issue of limited internet connection in schools, both male and female teachers expressed similar mean ratings, indicating that this problem affects both genders equally. The statement "There is no internet connection in our school" received a moderate mean rating for both males and females, highlighting the impact of limited internet access on the effective use of OER as an educational resource. Female teachers

reported slightly higher mean ratings for the statement "Digital resources are difficult for me to access" compared to their male counterparts. This suggests that female teachers may perceive accessing digital resources as relatively more challenging, indicating a potential gender difference in technology access and proficiency. Regarding the statement, "Digital materials can be presented outside their original context," female teachers gave higher mean ratings than male teachers. This indicates that female teachers may have stronger concerns about maintaining the contextual integrity of digital materials when utilizing them in their teaching. Additionally, female teachers expressed higher mean ratings for the statement "I don't want my students to copy or plagiarize material from the Web," indicating a greater concern about potential plagiarism when using online resources. This highlights their emphasis on promoting academic integrity among their students.

The findings suggest that while male and female teachers share some common concerns about the disadvantages of OER, there are subtle differences in their perceptions. Female teachers show slightly greater concerns about accessing digital resources, maintaining contextual integrity, and preventing plagiarism. These insights underscore the importance of addressing gender-specific concerns and providing appropriate support and training to help teachers effectively integrate OER into their teaching practices.

The findings are related to existing literature and studies that explore teachers' experiences and perceptions of Open Educational Resources (OER), particularly concerning gender differences in technology access and proficiency. The observation that female teachers reported slightly higher mean ratings for the statement "Digital resources are difficult for me to access" resonates with prior research highlighting gender discrepancies in technology literacy and access. This aligns with studies emphasizing the need for targeted support to address such disparities (Alenezi, 2020). Additionally, the higher mean ratings among female teachers for concerns related to maintaining contextual integrity and preventing plagiarism reflect their emphasis on academic integrity and ethical considerations in teaching practices, which echoes findings from studies emphasizing the importance of promoting ethical behavior and integrity in online learning environments (Bliss & Hilton, et.al., 2012). Therefore, these findings underscore the importance of tailored interventions and training programs that address gender-specific concerns and promote equitable access to resources and support for male and female teachers

The findings regarding teachers' experiences with Open Educational Resources (OER) in terms of educational attainment align with existing literature and studies on teachers' perceptions and challenges in utilizing digital resources. The observation that individuals with master's degrees express slightly higher concerns about accessing digital resources resonates with prior research emphasizing the importance of addressing technological proficiency and familiarity among educators, particularly those with higher levels of educational attainment (Alenezi, 2020). Similarly, the higher mean ratings among individuals with master's degrees for concerns related to maintaining contextual integrity and preventing plagiarism echo findings from studies emphasizing the importance of promoting academic integrity and ethical behavior in online learning environments (Bliss & Hilton, et.al., 2012).

Table 2.4.3

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Educational Attainment

The table 2.4.3 shows the mean scores for different statements about teachers experiences on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of educational attainment (male and female). The computed means are 2.95 and 3.28, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree.

Both groups of teachers expressed agreement with the statement "They cannot substitute for the teaching approaches I use." This suggests that both college graduates and individuals with master's degrees perceive limitations in the ability of OER to fully replace their preferred teaching methods. The mean ratings for this statement were relatively high for both groups, indicating a shared concern. Regarding the issue of limited internet connection in schools, both groups of teachers provided similar mean ratings, indicating that this challenge affects both college graduates and individuals with master's degrees equally. The statement "There is no internet connection in our school" received a moderate mean rating for both groups, highlighting the impact of limited internet access on the effective use of OER. When it comes to accessing digital resources, individuals with master's degrees (with units) gave slightly higher mean ratings compared to college graduates.

This suggests that those with higher educational attainment may perceive accessing digital resources as relatively more challenging, indicating a potential difference in their familiarity and comfort with technology. In terms of the statement "Digital materials can be presented outside their original context," individuals with master's degrees (with units) provided higher mean ratings compared to college graduates. This indicates that individuals with higher educational attainment may have stronger concerns about maintaining the contextual integrity of digital materials when utilizing them in their teaching. Additionally, individuals with master's degrees (with units) expressed higher mean ratings for the statement "I don't want my students to copy or plagiarize material from the Web," indicating a greater concern about potential plagiarism when using online resources. This highlights their emphasis on promoting academic integrity among their students.

The findings suggest that while both college graduates and individuals with master's degrees share some common concerns about the disadvantages of OER, there are slight differences in their perceptions. Individuals with higher educational attainment demonstrate slightly higher concerns about accessing digital resources, maintaining contextual integrity, and preventing plagiarism. These insights underscore the importance of providing appropriate support and training to help teachers at different educational levels effectively integrate OER into their teaching practices.

The findings regarding teachers' experiences with Open Educational Resources (OER) in terms of their educational attainment resonate with existing literature on OER adoption

and teacher perceptions (Villanueva & Dolom, 2018). Both college graduates and individuals with master's degrees express concerns about the limitations of OER in fully substituting their preferred teaching methods, echoing previous studies emphasizing the importance of OER customization and flexibility to accommodate diverse instructional approaches (Bliss & Hilton, 2012). Moreover, the similar mean ratings provided by both groups regarding challenges such as limited internet access in schools underscore the critical role of addressing infrastructure issues to ensure equitable access to digital resources, as highlighted in prior research on OER implementation barriers (Alshahrani, Ahmed, & Ward, 2017).

However, differences emerge in perceptions regarding accessing digital resources and concerns about contextual integrity and plagiarism. Individuals with higher educational attainment demonstrate slightly higher concerns about accessing digital resources and maintaining contextual integrity, suggesting the need for targeted support and training to address varying levels of technological proficiency among educators (Arinto, 2016). Additionally, their heightened concern about preventing plagiarism underscores the importance of promoting digital literacy skills and ethical use of online resources among both teachers and students, aligning with literature on intellectual property concerns and academic integrity in the context of OER adoption (Cooney, 2016).

Table 2.4.4

Teachers' Experiences on the Disadvantages of Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Terms of Length of Service

The table 2.4.4 shows the mean scores for different statements about teachers experiences on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of length of service (1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25 and 26-30). The computed means are 3.34, 2.86, 3.23, 3.29, 3.68 and 3.36, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree.

Teachers with 1-5 years of service provided the highest mean rating for the statement "I don't want my students to copy or plagiarize material from the Web." This suggests that teachers in the early years of their career place a significant emphasis on preventing plagiarism when using OER in their teaching. On the other hand, teachers with 6-10 years of service gave the lowest mean rating for the same statement, indicating a relatively lower concern about plagiarism compared to their less-experienced counterparts. The report "They cannot substitute for the teaching approaches I use" received relatively high mean ratings across all groups, indicating a shared concern among teachers about the limitations of OER in entirely replacing their preferred teaching methods. However, teachers with 1-5 years and 16-20 years of service provided the highest mean ratings for this statement, suggesting that teachers in these groups feel particularly strongly about the challenges of substituting their teaching approaches with OER. Regarding the availability of internet connection in schools, teachers with 21-25 years of service provided the highest mean rating, indicating a greater concern about limited internet access affecting

the use of OER. This group of teachers may have witnessed the evolution of digital resources and the importance of internet connectivity in educational settings.

The findings imply that teachers' length of service plays a role in shaping their perceptions of the disadvantages of OER. Teachers in the early years of their careers demonstrate a strong emphasis on preventing plagiarism and may be more cautious about using OER. In contrast, teachers with more years of service may have experienced the evolution of digital resources and have a heightened awareness of the challenges related to limited internet connectivity. The findings regarding teachers' experiences with Open Educational Resources (OER) in relation to their length of service align with existing literature on teacher perceptions and OER adoption (Villanueva & Dolom, 2019). The emphasis placed by teachers with 1-5 years of service on preventing plagiarism when using OER reflects a common concern among early-career educators about academic integrity and ethical use of online resources (Cooney, 2016). Conversely, the relatively lower concern about plagiarism among teachers with 6-10 years of service may indicate a shift in priorities or a growing familiarity with digital pedagogy over time, echoing studies on the evolving perceptions of technology integration among educators (Alshahrani, Ahmed, & Ward, 2017).

Moreover, the shared concern among teachers across all groups about the limitations of OER in fully substituting their preferred teaching methods resonates with literature emphasizing the need for customizable and adaptable OER to accommodate diverse instructional approaches (Bliss & Hilton, 2012). The heightened concern among teachers with 21-25 years of service regarding limited internet access underscores the significance of addressing infrastructure issues to facilitate effective OER use, consistent with prior research highlighting barriers related to technological accessibility in educational settings (Arinto, 2016). Overall, these findings emphasize the dynamic nature of teacher perceptions regarding OER adoption and highlight the importance of tailored professional development initiatives to support educators at different career stages in effectively integrating OER into their teaching practices.

Part III. The Test of Significant Difference on the Teachers' Experiences Using Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Profile Variables

Table 3

The Test of Significant Difference on the Teachers' Experiences Using Open Educational Resources When Grouped in Profile Variables

The table 3 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in teachers' experiences in using Open Educational Resources (OER) when the respondents are grouped by district and length of service. Specifically, the p-value of .024 for districts suggests a significant variation, implying that teachers' experiences with OER differ considerably depending on their geographical location. For instance, teachers in District

2, with a mean rank of 55.10, might have better access to OER training or resources compared to those in District 3, which has a mean rank of 32.10.

Similarly, the length of service also shows a significant difference, with a p-value of .003. This indicates that teachers' perceptions and utilization of OER vary with their years of experience. Teachers with 1-5 years and 21-25 years of service, both having a mean rank of 66.67, significantly differ in their experiences compared to those with 6-10 years, who have a mean rank of 31.86. This disparity might be due to newer teachers being more adaptable to technological changes and seasoned teachers having more exposure to various teaching methods, including OER.

Conversely, there is no statistically significant difference in teachers' experiences with OER when grouped by age, school category, educational attainment, and sex. The p-values for these variables (.179, .131, .113, and .113, respectively) suggest that these factors do not critically influence how teachers perceive and use OER. This indicates that regardless of their age, whether they teach in small, medium, or large schools, their level of educational attainment, or their gender, teachers have similar experiences with OER.

These findings align with previous studies that highlight the influence of contextual factors such as location and experience on the adoption and use of OER. For instance, Villanueva & Dolom (2019) emphasized the importance of contextual and individual factors in the adoption of OER. Additionally, Alenezi (2020) pointed out the varying readiness and capacity of different regions in adopting e-learning technologies, which can be extrapolated to OER. The significant impact of length of service on teachers' experiences with OER also correlates with Cooney's (2016) observation of varying engagement levels based on familiarity and comfort with technology. Therefore, while demographic factors may not significantly influence OER experiences, contextual variables like district and length of service are crucial, highlighting the need for tailored interventions and support systems to optimize OER adoption and use.

Part IV. The Problems Encountered by Teachers in Using Online Educational Resources Instructional Materials.

Table 4

The Problems Encountered by Teachers in Using Online Educational Resources Instructional Materials

The table 4 provided presents the problems encountered by teachers in using online educational resources instructional materials. The standard deviation is 0.938 with a mean rating of 3.32 which is verbally interpreted as neither agree or disagree.

Among the listed problems, "Technical difficulties with online teaching tools" received the highest mean rating of 3.80, falling under the interpretation of "Agree" (A). This indicates that a significant number of teachers encountered technical issues while using online teaching tools. These challenges may include difficulties with video conferencing platforms, file sharing, or other technical aspects of online instruction. The problem of

"Time consuming resources" received a mean rating of 3.32, also falling under the interpretation of "Neither agree nor disagree" (N). This suggests that teachers perceived online instructional materials as requiring considerable time and effort to use effectively. The time-consuming nature of these resources may include adapting and modifying materials for online delivery, creating engaging multimedia content, or providing additional support to students in virtual environments. "Lack of Computer literacy" and "Lack of technical/software knowledge" both received mean ratings of 3.32 and 3.46, respectively, falling under the interpretation of "Neither agree nor disagree" (N) and "Agree" (A). These ratings indicate that teachers faced challenges related to their own computer literacy and technical/software knowledge when using online instructional materials. These difficulties may involve navigating digital platforms, troubleshooting software issues, or effectively integrating technology into their teaching practice. The problems of "Difficult to motivate pupils" and "Lack of pupils' interest" received mean ratings of 3.07 and 2.94, respectively, falling under the interpretation of "Neither agree nor disagree" (N). This suggests that while some teachers encountered challenges in motivating students and generating interest in online instruction, the overall perception was more neutral. These challenges may stem from the limitations of online environments in fostering student engagement and interaction.

The findings imply that teachers faced several challenges when using online instructional materials. Technical difficulties, the time-consuming nature of resources, and lack of computer literacy and technical/software knowledge were identified as prominent issues. However, difficulties in motivating pupils and capturing their interest were perceived to be slightly less problematic. These findings highlight the importance of providing support, training, and resources to help teachers overcome the challenges associated with online instruction and optimize the use of online instructional materials.

The findings regarding the challenges encountered by teachers in using online instructional materials align with existing literature on technology integration in education and teacher perceptions of digital tools (Alenezi, 2020). The high mean rating for "Technical difficulties with online teaching tools" reflects a common concern among educators about the reliability and usability of digital platforms, consistent with previous research highlighting technical challenges as barriers to effective online instruction (Richardson et al., 2019). Similarly, the perceived time-consuming nature of online instructional materials resonates with literature emphasizing the importance of adequate time and resources for educators to develop and implement technology-enhanced teaching strategies (Cooney, 2016).

Moreover, the challenges related to teachers' computer literacy and technical/software knowledge are consistent with studies highlighting the need for ongoing professional development to support educators in building digital competencies and navigating technology-rich learning environments (Arinto, 2016). The findings also underscore the importance of addressing student motivation and engagement in online instruction, echoing research on the impact of technology on student motivation and learning outcomes (Hilton et al., 2012). Overall, these findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of challenges associated with online instruction and highlight the importance of

comprehensive support mechanisms to empower teachers in effectively leveraging digital tools for teaching and learning.

Part V. The Coping Strategies of Teachers in Addressing the Challenges

Table 5

The Coping Strategies of Teachers in Addressing the Challenges

The table 5 provided presents the coping strategies of teachers in addressing the challenges. The standard deviation is 0.770 with a mean rating of 4.11 verbally interpreted as agree.

"I keep my pupils engaged" received the highest mean rating of 4.14, falling under the interpretation of "Strongly Agree" (SA). This indicates that a significant number of teachers actively focus on keeping their students engaged in the learning process. By employing various instructional techniques, such as interactive activities, multimedia resources, and collaborative projects, teachers strive to enhance student engagement and participation in online instruction. "I let my pupils choose their learning way" also received a high mean rating of 3.97, falling under the interpretation of "Agree" (A). This suggests that teachers recognize the importance of providing students with autonomy in their learning. By allowing students to choose their learning paths and customize their learning experiences, teachers aim to foster a sense of ownership and motivation among students in the online environment.

"I invite my pupils to contribute to teachings" received a mean rating of 4.07, falling under the interpretation of "Agree" (A). This indicates that teachers actively encourage student contributions and participation in the instructional process. By involving students in discussions, collaborative projects, and decision-making, teachers create opportunities for active student engagement and promote a student-centered approach to online instruction. "I encourage peer evaluation" received a high mean rating of 4.16, falling under the interpretation of "Strongly Agree" (SA). This suggests that teachers emphasize the importance of peer evaluation as a valuable learning strategy. By incorporating peer assessment and feedback, teachers promote student collaboration, self-reflection, and the development of critical evaluation skills within the online learning environment. "I engage myself in ICT training" received the highest mean rating of 4.19, falling under the interpretation of "Strongly Agree" (SA). The result indicates that teachers actively participate in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) training to enhance their digital skills and pedagogical practices. Teachers strive to improve their instructional delivery and effectively integrate online instructional materials by continuously updating their knowledge and skills in utilizing educational technology tools.

The findings imply that teachers employ various coping strategies to address the challenges associated with online instructional materials. Strategies such as keeping students engaged, allowing student choice, inviting student contributions, encouraging peer evaluation, and engaging in ICT trainings are widely adopted by teachers. These strategies reflect a proactive approach to enhancing student engagement, promoting

student-centered learning, and improving the teachers' digital competencies within the online learning environment.

Moreover, the coping strategies that teachers employ to overcome challenges associated with online instructional materials. The data offers valuable insights into the adaptations made by educators within the context of online education.

The findings reveal several key observations. Firstly, teachers are deeply committed to maintaining high levels of student engagement which underscores their dedication to enhancing student participation and interaction in online learning environments. Secondly, teachers recognize the importance of providing students with autonomy in their learning journeys where in this strategy aims to empower students by granting them a sense of control over their learning experiences. Additionally, the practice of inviting students to actively contribute to teaching is prevalent which emphasizes the shift towards a more student-centered approach in online instruction, fostering greater participation and collaboration.

Furthermore, teachers place a strong emphasis on encouraging peer evaluation which promotes collaborative learning, self-reflection, and the development of critical evaluation skills among students. Lastly, teachers are actively investing in their professional development by participating in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) training where in underscores their commitment to enhancing digital skills and pedagogical practices for effective technology integration in teaching.

The teachers are collectively adopting proactive coping strategies to address the challenges posed by online instructional materials. These findings indicate a strong commitment to delivering high-quality online learning experiences. The proactive measures taken by teachers to navigate the complexities of online education. These strategies prioritize student engagement, autonomy, and participation, while also enhancing teachers' digital competencies. Educators are demonstrating a steadfast dedication to the advancement of online education, ensuring its continued effectiveness and success.

The findings regarding the coping strategies of teachers in addressing the challenges of online instructional materials resonate with existing literature on effective teaching practices in digital learning environments (Alenezi, 2020). The emphasis on keeping students engaged aligns with research highlighting the importance of active student participation and interaction for meaningful learning outcomes in online education. By employing strategies such as interactive activities and multimedia resources, teachers aim to create dynamic learning experiences that enhance student engagement and motivation, consistent with recommendations for effective online teaching.

Moreover, the focus on providing students with autonomy in their learning echoes literature on learner-centered approaches to online instruction, which emphasize the importance of empowering students to take ownership of their learning process. By allowing students to choose their learning paths and contribute to the instructional process, teachers promote a sense of autonomy and self-directed learning, which has

been associated with increased motivation and academic achievement in online settings.

Part VI. Development of Sample Online Educational Resources Instructional Materials

Open Educational Resources (OER) are learning, teaching and research materials in any format and medium that reside in the public domain or are under copyright that have been released under an open license, that permit no-cost access, re-use, re-purpose, adaptation and redistribution by others.

Any resource available on the internet in an online educational environment. It might be audio or video lessons, interactive exercises or exams, or documents providing links to other Web sites.

This is the examples of online educational resources instructional materials could be developed by the researcher the subject is about the Science 3 quarter 4 Week 7.

CONCLUSIONS

Summary

This study was aimed to the experiences of teachers in transitioning from textbooks to online instructional materials, basis for Open Education Resources utilization plan in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Quezon, School Year 2022-2023; awareness, online platforms being used, advantages and disadvantages, problems encountered, and coping strategies will be discussed in this study.

The respondents of the study were delimited to public elementary teachers in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Quezon.

Summary of Findings

From the thorough analysis of the data gathered and the results obtained in the previous discussion, the following significant findings are hereby summarized.

1. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 Age

The profile of the respondents. Most of the respondents fall within the age range of 26-45, accounting for 60% of the total respondents. Specifically, the age group of 26-35 comprises 33.3% of the respondents, followed by the age group of 36-45 with 26.7%. The age groups of 46-55 and 56-65 account for 28.9% and 11.1% of the respondents, respectively.

1.2 Sex

The respondents are predominantly female, representing 88.9% of the total participants. Male respondents constitute a relatively smaller percentage, making up 11.1% of the total respondents.

1.3 Educational Attainment

For educational Attainment, majority of the participants have a "College Graduate with masters units" educational background, representing 88.9% of the respondents. A smaller percentage, 11.1%, are college graduates.

1.4 Length of Service

The length of service distribution among the respondents are around 13.3% have 1-5 years of service, 23.3% have 6-10 years, another 13.3% have 11-15 years, approximately 24.4% have 16-20 years, around 11.1% have 21-25 years, and finally, about 14.4% have 26-30 years.

2. The teachers' experiences in using online educational resources (OER) in terms of following when grouped into demographic profile:

2.1.1 Experienced of the Existence of Online platforms based on the gathered data, the mean scores for different statements related to teachers' experiences of online platforms, categorized by different age groups (26-35, 36-45, 46-55, and 56-65). The computed means are 4.18, 4.02, 4.28, and 4.08, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as experienced.

2.1.2 The mean scores for different statements related to teachers' experiences of online platforms, categorized by different sex groups (male and female). The computed means of male group is 3.97 and for female group is 4.18, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as experienced.

2.1.3 Additionally, the data signifies the mean scores for different statements related to teachers experiences of online platforms in terms of educational attainment. The weighted mean for college graduate is 3.97 and for respondents with master is 4.18. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as agree.

2.1.4 Moreover, the mean scores for different statements about teachers' experiences of online platforms in terms of length in service (1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25 and 26-30). The computed means are 4.48, 4.06, 4.19, 3.97, 4.20 and 4.26, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.695 with a total mean of 4.15 which is verbally interpreted as agree.

2.2 The usage of various online platforms as instructional materials. Among the listed platforms, Messenger is the most frequently used, with a significant percentage of 62.2, making it the top-ranked platform. YouTube follows closely behind with 58.9, securing the second position. Google stands at the third rank with 44.4 usage. Other platforms utilized include Google Meet (32.2%), Google Classroom (27.8%), Instagram (10.0%), Skill share (11.1%), LinkedIn Learning (8.9%), Skype (3.3%), and Twitter (3.3%), all with relatively lower frequencies and percentages.

2.3 .1 Advantages of Open Educational Resources;

Based on the gathered data, the mean scores for different statements about Teachers experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of age (26-35, 36-45, 46-55 and 56-65). The computed means are 4.38, 4.21, 4.30 and 4.29, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.21 to 4.38, indicating a consistent positive perception of OER advantages among teachers across different age groups. The highest-rated statement is "It helps me get pupils excited about a topic" with a total mean rating of 4.41, suggesting that teachers, regardless of their age, recognize the ability of OER to engage students and generate enthusiasm for learning. Other statements that received high ratings include "It enhances course material" (mean rating of 4.38) and "It helps me improve my pupils' learning" (mean rating of 4.32). These results highlight the perceived benefits of using OER in terms of enriching course materials and enhancing student learning outcomes.

2.3.2 The mean scores for different statements about teachers' experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of sex (male and female). The computed means are 4.24 and 4.32, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree.

2.3.3 The mean scores for different statements about Teachers experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of educational attainment (college and master with units). The computed means are 4.24 and 4.32, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31 which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.10 to 4.44, with the grand mean being 4.31. These ratings suggest that both college graduates and individuals with master's units highly value OER's advantages in enhancing teaching and learning experiences.

2.3.4 The mean scores for different statements about Teachers experiences on the advantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of length of service (1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25 and 26-30). The computed means are 4.73, 4.21, 4.20, 4.15, 4.28, and 4.44, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 0.536 with a total mean of 4.31, which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. The mean ratings for all the statements range from 4.05 to 4.83, with the grand mean being 4.31. These high ratings indicate that

teachers with varying service lengths perceive OER's advantages positively, regardless of their experience in the field.

2.4.1 The mean scores for different statements about teachers experience on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of age (26-35, 36-45, 46-55 and 56-65). The computed means are 3.01, 3.17, 3.59 and 3.19, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree. The mean ratings for the statements range from 2.50 to 3.77, with a grand mean of 3.24. These ratings suggest that teachers express mixed opinions when it comes to perceiving the disadvantages of OER, influenced by their age group.

2.4.2 The mean scores for different statements about teachers experiences on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of sex (male and female). The computed means are 2.95 and 3.28, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree.

2.4.3 The mean scores for different statements about teachers experiences on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of educational attainment (college and female). The computed means are 2.95 and 3.28, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree.

2.4.4 The mean scores for different statements about teachers experience on the disadvantages of Open Educational Resources in terms of length of service (1-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25 and 26-30). The computed means are 3.34, 2.86, 3.23, 3.29, 3.68 and 3.36, respectively. The overall standard deviation is 1.042 with a total mean of 3.24, which is verbally interpreted as neither agree nor disagree.

3. The result of the study about the test of standard deviation of the teachers' experiences using open educational resources when grouped into profile variables revealed that there is a significant difference between teachers' experiences when it comes to their district and length of service. And there is no significant difference between teachers' experiences when grouped into their age, sex, school category, educational attainment and length of service.

4. Based on the gathered data, the problems encountered by teachers in using online instructional materials with the standard deviation is 0.938 and mean rating of 3.32 which is verbally interpreted as neither agree or disagree.

The problems faced by teachers when using online instructional materials. The highest mean rating was for "Technical difficulties with online teaching tools with 3.80, indicating that many teachers encountered issues with the functionality of online tools. "Time consuming resources" received a mean rating of 3.32, suggesting that teachers perceived online materials as requiring significant time and effort. "Lack of Computer literacy with 3.32 and "Lack of technical/software knowledge with 3.46 with mean. Indicates challenges related to teachers' own skills in using technology. "Difficult to motivate pupils" with 3.07 and "Lack of pupils' interest 2.94 highlight challenges in engaging students in online learning, although the perception was more neutral.

5. The coping strategies of teachers in addressing the challenges.

The standard deviation is 0.770 with a mean rating of 4.11 verbally interpreted as agree. The highest mean rating was for "I keep my pupils engaged" (4.14), indicating that teachers make a significant effort to ensure student engagement in the learning process. While the lowest mean is "I let my pupils choose their learning way" received a mean rating of 3.97, suggesting that teachers value student autonomy in online learning. "I invite my pupils to contribute to teachings" (4.07) highlights teachers' encouragement of student participation and contributions. "I encourage peer evaluation" (4.16) indicates that teachers emphasize peer assessment as a valuable learning strategy. Lastly, "I engage myself in ICT training" received the highest mean rating of 4.19, illustrating that teachers actively seek professional development to improve their digital skills and pedagogical practices.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The demographic profile of the respondents indicates that the majority of participants are in the age range of 26-45, predominantly female, have a "Masters with units" educational background, and have varying lengths of service.
2. Teachers' experiences regarding online platforms show that they have a generally positive perception and awareness of these platforms, regardless of their age, gender, educational attainment, or length of service.
3. Regarding Open Educational Resources (OER), teachers perceive significant advantages in terms of engaging students, enhancing course materials, and improving learning outcomes. These positive perceptions remain consistent across different age groups, genders, educational backgrounds, and lengths of service. However, when it comes to the disadvantages of OER, teachers express mixed opinions, indicating that their perceptions may be influenced by various factors, including age.
4. Teachers face several challenges in using online instructional materials, including technical difficulties, time-consuming resources, lack of computer literacy, lack of technical/software knowledge, and difficulties in motivating students and generating student interest. These challenges highlight the need for support in terms of technical assistance, training, and strategies to foster student engagement and motivation. Overall, these findings emphasize the need for support in addressing technical issues, saving time, enhancing computer literacy, and promoting student motivation.
5. To address these challenges, teachers employ coping strategies such as keeping students engaged, allowing student choice in learning, encouraging student contributions, emphasizing peer evaluation, and actively participating in ICT training. These strategies reflect the commitment of teachers to enhance student engagement, collaboration, and their own professional development in the online learning environment. However, it is equally clear that teachers employ coping strategies and have positive experiences with online platforms in open educational resources.

6. Provide teachers with necessary support, resources, and training to effectively navigate online instruction and maximize student learning outcomes. By addressing the challenges and leveraging the coping strategies employed by teachers, educational institutions can foster a conducive online learning environment and ensure quality education for students. The researcher could develop of sample online educational resources instructional material that the researcher would use during blended modular distant learning caused of heat wave of extremely heat that experienced of the student.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn from the analysis, the following recommendations can be made to support teachers in addressing the challenges of online instruction and maximizing the benefits of technology in education:

1. The findings revealed that the most of the respondents predominantly have a master with units' educational background and the college graduate have a smaller percentage. Consequently, the school administrators may provide comprehensive and ongoing professional development programs that focus on enhancing teachers' digital skills, pedagogical strategies, and familiarity with online teaching tools. This training should cover areas such as effective use of online platforms, multimedia resources, and student engagement techniques in the virtual classroom.
2. Based on the gathered data teachers' experiences regarding online platforms show that they have a generally positive perception and awareness of these platforms. The school may establish a dedicated technical support system to assist teachers in resolving technical issues and overcoming challenges related to online teaching tools.
3. The significant differences revealed the teachers' experiences using open educational resources that there is a significant difference between teachers' experiences. The school may foster the development and sharing of high-quality online instructional materials, including Open Educational Resources (OER). Encourage teachers to collaborate and create engaging and interactive content that aligns with the curriculum objectives and meets the diverse learning needs of students in the online environment.
4. Based on the gathered data these findings emphasize the need for support in addressing technical issues and promoting student motivation. Recommendation includes the encouragement of teachers to adopt a variety of student engagement strategies, such as interactive activities, collaborative projects, and multimedia resources.
5. Based on the comprehensive analysis of the gathered data that teachers face the coping strategies of teachers in addressing the challenges, the school as a community may create a supportive and inclusive online learning environment that values student contributions and encourages active participation. Establish channels for communication and collaboration among students, teachers, and

parents to promote a sense of belonging and provide opportunities for ongoing support and feedback.

The future researcher promotes peer collaboration and evaluation as valuable learning strategies. Encourage teachers to facilitate peer assessment and feedback to foster student collaboration, critical thinking, and self-reflection.

6. Further study on challenges of online instruction and maximizing the benefits of technology in education, the future researcher could develop of sample online educational resources instructional materials that uses as online educational resources during the modular distant learning caused of extremely heat of climate.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to the research ethics of anonymity, consent, and beneficence. the research ensured that the data gathered were secured and observed with the utmost consideration of data privacy. no personal information provided by the respondents was divulged in the study. in addition, the teachers who provided the data of learners were given a copy of the consent form to ensure they were aware of their participation. The researcher explained in full detail the process of data gathering and assured that the data shall be treated with the utmost confidentiality. The teachers were also given the option to withdraw their participation if they felt there was a need for them to do so. Finally, the researcher informed the respondents that no benefits shall be provided to the respondents but the data they will be providing shall be helpful for the realizations and completion of the study.

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